

The Impact of Religion and Politics in Nigeria: The Tiv Experience

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Abstract

Nigeria is a diverse nation characterised by multi-ethnic groups, with religions and a complex interplay of religious beliefs and political structures that significantly shape its socio political and economic lifestyle. The Tiv people of Central Nigeria has a distinct religious and cultural identity that shows a good relationship between religion and politics. The intertwining relationship between religion and politics in Nigeria is a compelling subject as it underpins many aspects of the nation's life, including governance, social norms, and public engagement. Although Christianity and Islam are adopted religions, they have combined forces with traditional religion to exert much influence on the political landscape of Nigeria. Among the Tiv, the influence of religion on politics is highly noticeable as can be seen in political decisions, electoral behaviours, and policy-making processes. This paper using descriptive method, examines the concepts of religion and politics, it discusses the relationship between religion and politics, and identified the impact/relationship it has on the Tiv of Central Nigeria. The paper maintained that though Christianity and Islam played their part in Nigerian politics, traditional religion also has a major part in political life of the Tiv and this would not be easily to wipe out in a near future. Suggestions were made to include the need to uphold religious norms and values practiced in ancient Tiv days, which aimed at general development of Tivland. Politics should not be seen as an avenue for making money but a fair representative and those politicians should give room for a credible, free and fair election so as to enjoy politics, development, and growth in Nigeria.

Keywords: Religion, Politics, Nigeria, Tiv, Socio-political landscape

Introduction

Nigeria, a diverse nation characterised by multi-ethnicity, experiences a complex interplay of religious beliefs and political structures that significantly shape its societal dynamics. The Tiv, primarily residing in central Nigeria, represent a significant ethnic group with their own distinct religious and cultural identity. Nigeria is made up of different ethnic groups, with diverse religious and political orientations. One among the ethnic groups in Nigeria is the Tiv who are found in different states of the country. They are primarily residing in central Nigeria; with their distinct religious and cultural identity. The intertwining of religion and politics in Nigeria is a compelling subject as it underpins many aspects of the nation's life, including governance, social norms, and public engagement. Christianity, introduced during the colonial period, has become deeply rooted in Nigerian societies, including the Tiv, influencing political decisions, electoral behaviours, and policy-making processes. However, it is essential to recognize that traditional African religious beliefs, deeply ingrained in the Tiv culture, also hold sway over their political engagements. Religion is the core aspect in human nature, for it has eaten deep into human fabrics.

Religious beliefs and practices have contributed both positively and negatively to human beings. Among Africans, and Tiv in particular, religion has permeated all departments of human affairs. This made John S. Mbiti to say that, Africans are notoriously religious and that each people have a religious system with set of beliefs and practices.¹ Religious beliefs and practices provide ways in which humanity ought to follow. It is this thinking that I. A. Jawondo depict man as both religious and political animal.² Though Aristotle describes man as a political

animal. The engagement of man in political affairs by use of force, threat whether directly or indirectly gives him an upper hand in power play whether or not he likes it.

Man's nature is different from other creatures and as such he is the only being that has a religion, which implies that, religion is a universal activity practiced in all human society in different ways with great seriousness by her adherents. This paper examines the impact of religion and politics on Nigeria using Tiv as a case study. It highlights how religion and politics are practiced and their contributions to the development of Tiv nation. The paper places emphasis on the two dominant religions practice by the Tiv (Christianity and African Traditional Religion), thereby outlining their impacts side by side.

Tiv of Central Nigeria

The name Tiv conveys a triple meaning. It is the name of the patriarchal ancestor believed to be the progenitor of the Tiv. It connotes the name of an ethnic group and it is the language spoken by them. To Tesemchi Makar, Tiv is a cultural group as well as the father of the Tiv people.³ Thus, the socio-cultural aspects of the name Tiv be from their ethnicity, their family's occupation, their social and political class, their religious beliefs and cosmic forces they follow, etc. It also expresses the values, ethics, and beliefs of the culture they are born into. To this, Akiga gives a vivid description of who the Tiv are:

They are a stickily built, virile race of farmers, whose two great aims in life are to fill their yam store and granaries with food, and their homes with children; an independent people, who have little respect for princes and have never felt the need for cohesion, or obedience to a central authority, or unifying code. There are cheerful contended and unafraid of tangible foes or misfortunes. They are always on guard against unseen evil forces and the occult machinations of their fellow men.⁴

It is very difficult to trace the origin of the Tiv in general because; no one appears to be quite sure of how or when they came to be where they are today. Thus, researchers rely completely on information from oral tradition, historical and archaeological sources for the study of the general history of the Tiv of central Nigeria. Tesemchi Makar traced the origin of Tiv to *Swem*, according to him, *Swem* is a mountain located about thirty-six miles south-west of the compound of a man called Yaro Gusa in the district of Nyievmbashaya. Yaro's compound is located on the mountain a mile away from Cameroon border.⁵ Tiv oral tradition has it that, Tiv originated from *Swem*. He further posits that, to the Tiv *Swem* is one of the mysteries of their homeland. It was here that the two sons of Tiv; Ichongo and Ipusu become aware of their Tivness. The descendant of Ichongo and Ipusu constitutes not only the genealogical tree but also the basis of the social and political organisation of the Tiv society.⁶ *Swem* to the Tiv people is more than just a place of settlement; It is also a symbol of justice that is why, in Tiv society, when one swears falsely on *Swem*, he dies. For the purpose of this paper, we opt for the *Swem* pedigree theory. Andrew P. Adegas posit that The Tiv are predominantly found in Benue state and also found as indigenes of Taraba, Nasarawa and Plateau state as well as Cameroon. A considerable number of Tiv are found in Kwara, Niger, the FCT and South-western states who engaged in farming activities.⁷ In the Benue valley, the Tiv occupied fertile land, which enables the people engage in agricultural activities. The socio-political organisation of the Tiv people begins with *ya* unit (compound to Tar (Tivland)).

The Concept of Religion

Religion is the belief in supernatural power that man considers superior to him that calls for his submission and dependence for his wellbeing. Religion has no universally accepted definition just because religion interests people from various backgrounds who define the concepts from their own perspectives. However, according to Kyernum Nyamibo, religion is seen as the belief and practice that is made manifest in the management of a relationship that exists consciously and unconsciously between the temporal and the spiritual worlds with particular reference to a group of people. Whatever dimension one takes, religion involves the belief and practices of a group of people with efforts to maintain a cordial relationship between the spiritual, and the temporal worlds

to harness the full benefits of such relationship.⁸ The Tiv traditional Religion is centred on *Aondo*, (God) *tsav*, (Witchcraft) *akombo* (Cosmic forces and rituals) and *Adzov* (Spirits). In the contemporary Tiv society, African religion and Christianity are more popular and have both affected the Tiv politics.

The Concept of Politics

Politics involves the efforts by politicians to scheme for power especially in a democratic government. According to Nguveren Kyernum, politics is a process by which a group of people make collective and binding decisions to organize and control the activities others in the society. It is the art and science of governance involving all members of the society. It equally involves social relations defined by authority and legitimacy of public policy.⁹ It is all about who makes policy and the implementation of such policies, distribution and redistribution of resources. In order to achieve this, individuals form political parties or associations to mobilize voters to support their interests, concern and advantage. In the process, there is rivalry and competition whereby the use of money and spiritual resources are required. Religion then becomes indispensable, as consultations are needed on spiritual needs concerning party politics.

The Relationship between Politics and Religion

Politics and religion have a very cordial relationship. All religions practice in Nigeria has impact on Nigerian politics and vice versa. Politicians depend on both religions in search of power or governance. These can be seen in the role sacred authorities' play in Nigerian politics.

The Role of Traditional Sacred Authorities

Nigerians consult the sacred authorities in their search for power. At times, rainmakers are consulted to control rainfall when political rallies are to be held especially in public squares during rainy seasons. Again, sacrifices are offered to secure the safety of campaigners and vehicles used by politicians. The medicine men enjoy high patronage as they prepare medicine that would attract the voters to a politician and a political party. It is believed that a politician with high quality of African medicine speaks more convincingly than a trained orator. Among the Tiv, the medicine and cosmic ritual called *Ikyohol-ior* (Crowd gathering) is highly used by many politicians. This is in line with Kyernum Nyamibo's view that:

Nigerians consult African religious sacred authorities such as medicine men, diviners, sorcerer, mediums, priests and ancestors to know their fate in an electioneering endeavour. Charms and amulets are obtained from African specialists for Protection, good luck among others. Many thugs when arrested or die accidentally, among many things collected from them include; assorted charms and amulets. Whether these are efficacious or not is not even the issue. The truth is that the politicians cannot do without African medicine even those who claim loyalty to alien religions of Christianity and Islam. When they achieve, they organize exorbitant thanks giving services in the church while rituals are equally performed under cover to fulfil their spiritual obligations to ancestors, and African religious sacred specialists.¹⁰

Songs play a vital role in electioneering campaigns; for it educates voters and portrays a candidate as the most qualified for the keenly contested post by aspirants of different political parties. The praise singers rely heavily on African medicine in composition of these songs. Thus, these traditional songs have contributed to politics among Tiv people. Again, the zoning formula of many political parties follows the traditional religious belief of the people and is sanctioned by elders and kings who are often the custodians of African Religion. In traditional religious communities, the paramount rulers play the dual role of socio-political heads as well as priests of their traditional religious community. They are custodians of their religious value system and therefore, wield much political power in their domains. Politicians receive royal blessings from the kings before embarking on their political endeavours. M. K. Ashante identify the role of kings when they say: "kings serve their constituents by representing their traditions, culture and aspirations as divine and ethical imperative, and conversely, they

serve the divine through their capacity as high priest and caretaker of the people.”¹¹ In summary, kings perform the following functions:

- i) Kings function as the conduit between the sacred cosmos of the ancestors and spiritual entities and the mundane affairs of everyday human activities.
- ii) They serve as both the head of state and head of religion.
- iii) He is the leader and arbitrator of family, clan and nation.
- iv) Ritual specialist and mediator for the spirit world and living community.
- v) He is a guardian of cultural legacy and traditions.
- vi) He is the upholder and defender of social propriety and justice.
- vii) He gives royal blessings to political aspirants and office holders.

In the light of the above, kings are therefore, indispensable in Nigerian politics. Whatever contributions the traditional rulers make in Nigerian democracy; it is part of what African religion is doing to sustain the democracy of the country. African religion provides morality and regulates how politics is carried out in the society. The traditional African societies lived communal lives, which recognized the importance of each member of the society. Sanctions are provided against erring members of the society. When there are factions in a political party, the traditional institution comes in for arbitration. This regulates the society and paves way for the survival of democracy.

Swem is the Tiv symbol of justice used for oath-taking. It is both spiritual and physical, and its spirituality binds the people through which truth, equality, honesty, sincerity, justice is adhered by the Tiv. *Swem* summons the power of the community to carry out justice. According to Sarwuan D. Shishima, *swem* is capable of judging and killing anyone who swears by it falsely using *ijembe Aondo*. He further maintains that, if a person is accused of *tsav*, especially for causing misfortune, disease or death of another person, the suspect swears publicly by *swem*. After decoration of the *swem* by the elders, the suspect takes oath stating his case. In this case, he binds witches by the oath and hopes for justice and peace.¹²

Again, rituals are performed for the survival of Nigerian society as a whole by the priests. They offer prayers, pronounce blessings as well as pour libation as the need arises. The priest is the chief custodian of religious emblems, objects, myths and traditions. Awolalu and Dopamu cited in Kyernum Nyamibo sum up the religious functions of the priest when they say:

...is the official servant of a divinity; He is the mediator between God or divinity or divinities and man. He serves as a link between the worshipper and the object of worship. He knows the divinity, hears him and speaks to him for himself and other worshippers. As the mouthpiece of the divinity, he takes messages from him and delivers them to the people in essence; he is the embodiment of the presence of God among his people.¹³

The priests officiate at festivals, shrines to secure blessings for the community. However, the changing roles of priest due to influence of materialism and corruption is what has constituted a challenge sacred authorities pose to the peace and stability of the country.

Christianity and Politics in Tivland

Christianity plays a key role in development; educational wise, the missionaries open schools for educational activities which help in preaching the gospel in Tivland. The only way the European missionaries could achieve their mission was through education. Education serves as bedrock which they used since they did not understand Tiv language. Western education was introduced in Tivland and spearheaded by the missionaries, for they need to teach the people the Bible and the word of God. According to Shagbaor F. Wegh, the Protestants started educational development in Tivland as early as 1911, when they opened the first school ever to be established on Tiv soil at Sai in Shitile.¹⁴ Today, the church is leading in the establishment of educational institutions in Benue state. Many popular politicians in the state are the products of these institutions. Today, clergies contest and win elections and some are now political office holders by taking the advantage of the church

population as voters. These schools are good rendezvous for political rallies and socio religious activities. Tiv language was only spoken orally, there was no documented written form; but the coming of the missionaries helps in giving Tiv alphabets and a written form.

They also introduced Arabic numbers and helped in the translation of the Bible in Tiv. This view is supported by Kyernum Nyamibo when he says that the contribution of the church to the conservation and development of Tiv language outshines in the fact that the language initially was entirely oral. The church introduced the English alphabets into the language, and transcribed their pronunciation using their accents.¹⁵ Today, there are publications in Tiv language that are very informative about political trends in the state in particular and Nigeria in general. The church has become good campaign platforms in the name of thanksgiving, harvest birthday, and marriage anniversary services. There, politicians are given opportunity to sell their candidature to the church. Moreover, in case, the opponent belongs to another religion, it becomes a strong factor in politicking. At times, denominational dichotomy plays active part in whom to support or vote for during election.

The Impact of Politics and Religion on Tivland

Tiv traditional religion has contributed to the development of Tivland positively and at the same time; acts as a source of conflict. The Tiv practice of *akombo* and *tsav* has had a great impact to the individual practitioner and the society at large. For instance, the prosperity ignited by *imborivungu* has led to the production of political elites, development of markets, establishment of educational institutions and social amenities. To this, traditional religion has contributed their quota to the development Nigerian politics. On the other hand, Tiv religious practice has had negative consequence on the individual practitioner and the community at large. The misuse of *tsav* (witchcraft) and *akombo* (ritual) in the contemporary Tiv society is alarming. For instance, some Tiv politicians would buy rituals only to harm their opponents in other political parties. This brings fears to other aspirants and it is a setback for many people. Base on this, many people are afraid of involving themselves in politics.

Politics as practiced in Nigeria has a mixture of both positive and negative consequences. As a concept, G. Aberian and S. Masannat maintains that politics is a phenomenon, which has its origin in the class of individual preferences, its process in the public demands for accommodation of competing goals and its output in the form of binding public policies.¹⁶ In Nigeria for instance, different ethnic groups have since evolved a political philosophy and took active participation in politics. The Tiv people shared in this political ideology, and as well produced leaders who have contributed to nation building. The participation of Tiv in politics has tremendous contributions to national politics and development. At almost each and every developmental level, the Tiv people are involved. For instance; Mvendaga Jibo recorded that, during the Provisional Ruling Council, Late John Mark Inienger, served as the military governor of Bendel state from 1985-87 and also as the Brigade of Guards from 1988-1989.¹⁷ Inienger occupied several offices and even after the aborted coup by Gideon Orka a Tiv son, Babangida still retained the trust he had on him.

Another distinguished officer is Victor Samuel Leonard Malu who served as the ECOMOG Field commander in Sierra Leone and Liberia during the Abacha era from December, 1996-April 1998. He held many command and staff appointments on his rise to the top. When he served as ECOMOG Field Commander, he was very effective and was commended by the international community. Inienger and Malu earned a great deal of respect among their colleagues for their professionalism. Politically, they had limited impact, especially Malu who was indifferent to politics. For example, he was indifferent to the creation of more states and local governments which interested his colleagues like Brig-Gen. David Mark.¹⁸ The departure of Babangida from office featured the up-coming Tiv Politician, Barnabas A. I. Gemade, who was Secretary of works in the Babangida's cabinet, which was bequeathed to Ernest Shonekan. Gemade embraced partisan politics after the exit of Ibrahim Babangida and became very influential in the post-Babangida era. He played a critical role which produced George Akume as the governor of Benue State in 1999. This has produced several politicians whose contributions have yielded a fruitful result in Benue state and Nigeria at large. Mention must be made of Iorchia

Ayu, David Iornem and Iyorwuese Hagher, Very Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu, Gabriel Torwua Suswam, Mike Aondoakaa (SAN), Justice Kastina Alu (CJN). Dr Paul Orhii former DG NAFDAC and Mrs Farrida Mzamber Waziri of EFCC and a host of others who served in different capacities in a bid to contribute to nation building. Despite the huge contributions made by Tiv sons and daughters in nation building, back home, their involvement in politics has had negative impacts which are outlined below.

The Nature of Tiv Politics

Tiv political landscape is characterised by the following features:

Saa ma ilu mo/ hua (Must-Win-Syndrome or self-centredness/Greed) Politics is a game that can be won or lost; it is never a do-or die affair. However, most Tiv politicians have deliberately refused to be in touch with this inevitable reality. Therefore, in the bid to ensure victory at all cost, our electoral polls in the recent times have remained nothing better than open camps for electoral formalities, where civil rights and liberties as well as political offices are sold, bought and of course snatched. Relatedly, some politicians even when it is not their turn to contest, they key in, so as to contribute in destroying the system. To this, the Tiv philosophy of *Ya na Angbian* (Eat and give your relation) is fast eroding for the winner takes it all.

Political Godfathers: Political godfatherism as practice among Tiv politics is void of the true meaning of godfatherism, whose duty is to guide, protect, advice and direct. The political godfathers in Tivland gives help to their benefactors with the hope of receiving something greater in return. Even when they are serving at the national level, they want to detect on how their godson runs his government. They therefore subject their beneficiary to make a firm promise or undertake an oath to protect their interest. Once this oath is not respected, the godfather goes mad and wild; it is said, he can blackmail, kill or maim etc. This does not portrays well with Tiv politics in this contemporary age where politicians in other state look forward for developing their constituencies, their own is to cause confusion which led to underdevelopment. This godfatherism establishes political lords who have illegal machinery to enthrone anybody, even against the will of the people.

Politics of Hate Speech/ “Pull Him Down (PhD)” Syndrome: Politics in Tivland is faced with different problems. There exist antagonism, terror, rancour and acrimony. Political campaigns are not based on ideologies or issues oriented but rather they are characterised by boisterous denigration and blackmail. One’s affliction is not known until one dares to contest. Their campaign songs testify to this fact. For example, during campaign in 2019 and after election, there was a song sang by PDP that *ashabuku kwagh beer ve senator wough gande kimbir*. (The drunkard, your political ambition is over; you will not go back to senate again). In the same manner, APC sang a song accrediting Ortom as Tyongi (a man in ancient Tiv who owns numerous debts). Song like Ortom *wan moo, we ude kwagh Alia ga u hingir yam mjoko* (Ortom as you did not stop Alia matter you have become mchoko (house mouse) meat). Such hate speech is not healthy for the development of politics in Tivland yet they are practice on daily basis. In a similar development, during campaigns and after election, candidates take pleasure in the media or other public gatherings to accuse, blackmail, abuse and insult opponents. In contemporary Tiv society, the youth have turned the social media into an avenue of insulting politicians who even mean well for the development of the state.

Politics of Thuggery: Tiv politics is characterized by thuggery. The use of thugs during and after election is the common practice by almost all politicians. Among the Tiv for instance, politicians mobilize and recruit uneducated and unemployed youths as thugs to protect their sponsors and unleash violence and havoc on their opponents. In most cases, some of these thugs are rewarded with appointment or elective positions e.g. Ghana Akwaza, a notorious terrorist was appointed by Gov. Samuel Ortom to oversee revenue in Zone A Senatorial District of Benue state. Some of these thugs are sponsored by their principles to carried crime on their opponent. 25 It is interesting to note that, some Tiv people who nursed an ambition to contest for elective position, but seen as a threat by their opponent lost their lives through the activities of the thugs. Thugs make bold to introduce themselves as a politician’s thug (Mngu Tug u....). They negotiate for employment of people in the civil service under stringent conditions.

Recommendations

Religion and politics have played a vital role in shaping the Tiv society. Therefore, the Tiv people should imbibe positive values which religion provides for peaceful coexistence that promote the political stability of her society. Religious norms and values practiced in ancient Tiv days which lead to development should be reconnected while politics should not be seen as an avenue for making money but a fair representative. Since religion is an agent of social control which helps in keeping the norms of the society, which is the basis for politics, politicians in Tivland should give room for a credible, free and fair election if rarely they adhere to their religious practices. If such is done, the people will witness development, and growth. There will be unity and the challenges of insecurity will be a thing of past. Both adherents of religious practices and politicians should have respect on human lives and expunge ritual killing of any kind. Above all, the Tiv people should revive their philosophy of *ya na angbian* (eat and give your brother) and eliminate sentiment.

Conclusion

The paper examines the impact of religion and politics in Nigeria using Tiv people as a reference point. It is established that religion and politics influences have both positive and negative implications for the development of Tiv society. The work observed that religious organizations have greatly deviated from the core value of their norms while politicians in contemporary Tiv society employed mechanism for their self-interest. In spite of this, religion continues to influence political decisions for a successive development of Tivland and Benue state in general. This benefit could only be achieved if both practitioners shade off their differences and unite together for effective development.

Endnotes

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